

MERICS DATA INSIGHTS

QUANTUM

TECHNOLOGY

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Quantum technologies are emerging as a key stage of global power competition due to their possible applications in the military and their potential to fundamentally transform life.

Anhui, an eastern inland province with middling GDP and middling population, issues a lot of policy documents mentioning quantum. This is not the case for other technologies like semiconductors.

ANHUI LEADS IN QUANTUM POLICIES

Number of normative announcements by province (2015-2023)

Hefei, Anhui's capital, is home to the prestigious Chinese Academy of Sciences Key Laboratory of Quantum Information Sciences at the University of Science and Technology of China (USTC). It employs a research staff of 54, in addition to 141 students pursuing a PhD and 25 postdoctoral researchers, according to its website.

China's leading quantum scientist **Pan Jian-Wei**, who did a PhD in Vienna and worked as a postdoctoral researcher in Heidelberg, focuses on quantum communication. He largely contributed to China being most advanced in this field, while trailing the United States in both quantum computing and quantum sensing.

EXPERT TAKE

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“The centralization of quantum technologies around Pan Jian-Wei, who was partly educated in Austria and Germany, has generated good results for China. But it has also made it easy for the US to target China’s quantum sector by including 22 entities on its list of trade-restricted companies, thereby forbidding US firms from providing technology to them.”

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